

РАЗДЕЛ. ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

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ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF THE MEDIUM WITH ITS VISCOPLASTIC COURSE IN THE GAP BETWEEN COAXIAL CYLINDRICAL SURFACES

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Annotation: The rectilinear motions of a viscoplastic medium have been studied repeatedly [1, 2]. It turned out that it was possible to take into account the influence of the elastic properties of the medium on the parameters of such movements only within the framework of the theory of large deformations. It was on this basis that the first solutions to some model problems [3, 4] about the rectilinear motion of elastoviscoplastic media with subsequent unloading were obtained. In this note, we will construct an exact analytical solution to the boundary value problem of the theory of large elasto-viscoplastic deformations about the motion of a medium in the gap between coaxial cylindrical surfaces, when the outer one is stationary, and the inner one moves initially accelerated, followed by an equally slow stop. The nature of the movement of elastoplastic boundaries is indicated and the residual stresses in the material are calculated.

Keywords: viscoplastic medium, elasto-viscoplastic deformation, rectilinear motion, coaxial cylindrical surface, elastoplastic boundary

УПРУГИЕ СВОЙСТВА СРЕДЫ С ЕЕ ВЯЗКОПЛАСТИЧНЫМ ПРОХОДОМ В ЗАЗОРЕ МЕЖДУ КОАКСИАЛЬНЫМИ ЦИЛИНДРИЧЕСКИМИ ПОВЕРХНОСТЯМИ

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Аннотация: Прямолинейные движения вязкопластической среды изучались неоднократно [1, 2]. Оказалось, что учесть влияние упругих свойств среды на параметры таких движений можно только в рамках теории больших деформаций. Именно на этой основе были получены первые решения некоторых модельных задач [3, 4] о прямолинейном движении упруговязкопластических сред с последующей разгрузкой. В данной заметке мы построим точное аналитическое решение краевой задачи теории больших упруговязкопластических деформаций о движении среды в зазоре между соосными цилиндрическими поверхностями, когда внешняя из них неподвижна, а внутренняя движения сначала ускоряются, а затем столь же медленно останавливаются. Указан характер движения упругопластических границ и рассчитаны остаточные напряжения в материале.

Ключевые слова: вязкопластическая среда, упруговязкопластическая деформация, прямолинейное движение, коаксиальная цилиндрическая поверхность, упругопластическая граница

1. Basic model relationships

To solve the problem, we will use the model of large elastoplastic deformations proposed in [2, 5]. In a Cartesian rectangular system of spatial Euler coordinates x_i , the components of the reversible (elastic) e_{ij} and irreversible (plastic) p_{ij} , the experimentally not measurable components of the Almansi strain tensor d_{ij} , are determined by differential equations of change (transfer) in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{De_{ij}}{Dt} &= \varepsilon_{ij} - \varepsilon_{ij}^p - \frac{1}{2} \left((\varepsilon_{ik} - \varepsilon_{ik}^p + z_{ik})e_{kj} + e_{ik}(\varepsilon_{kj} - \varepsilon_{kj}^p - z_{kj}) \right), \\ \frac{Dp_{ij}}{Dt} &= \varepsilon_{ij}^p - p_{ik}\varepsilon_{kj}^p - \varepsilon_{ik}^p p_{kj}, \\ \frac{Dn_{ij}}{Dt} &= \frac{dn_{ij}}{dt} - r_{ik}n_{kj} + n_{ik}r_{kj}, \quad \varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(v_{i,j} + v_{j,i}), \quad v_i = \frac{du_i}{dt} = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + u_{i,j}v_j, \quad (1.1) \\ z_{ij} &= A^{-1} \{ B^2(\varepsilon_{ik}e_{kj} - e_{ik}\varepsilon_{kj}) + B(\varepsilon_{ik}e_{ks}e_{sj} - e_{ik}e_{ks}\varepsilon_{sj}) + \\ &\quad e_{ik}e_{ks}e_{st}e_{tj} - e_{ik}e_{ks}\varepsilon_{st}e_{tj} \}, \\ A &= 8 - 8E_1 + 3E_1^2 - E_2 - \frac{1}{3}E_1^3 + \frac{1}{3}E_3, \quad B = 2 - E_1, \end{aligned}$$

$$E_1 = e_{kk}, E_2 = e_{ij}e_{ji}, E_3 = e_{ij}e_{jk}e_{ki}, r_{ij} = w_{ij} + z_{ij}, w_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(v_{i,j} - v_{j,i}).$$

In relations (1.1) u_i, v_j are the components of displacement vectors and velocities of points of the medium, the symbol $\frac{D}{Dt}$ denotes the objective continuity of tensors in time, the source ε_{ij}^p in the equation for changing the tensor p_{ij} should, as in the classical theory, be called components of the plastic velocity tensor deforming, r_{ij} is the tensor of rotations and deformation rates. According to equations (1.1), under unloading conditions ($\varepsilon_{ij}^p = 0$), the components of the irreversible deformation tensor p_{ij} change as if the body were moving violently. The components of the Almansi complete deformation tensor d_{ij} through its components e_{ij} and p_{ij} are represented in the form

$$d_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i} - u_{k,i}u_{k,j}) = e_{ij} + p_{ij} - \frac{1}{2}e_{ik}e_{kj} - e_{ik}p_{kj} - p_{ik}e_{kj} + e_{ik}p_{kn}e_{mj}. \quad (1.2)$$

The stresses in the medium are completely determined by reversible deformations and, following the laws of thermodynamics, for an incompressible medium they are related to them by the dependencies

$$\sigma_{ij} = -p\delta_{ij} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial d_{ik}}(\delta_{ij} - 2d_{kj}) \text{ at } p_{ij} \equiv 0, \sigma_{ij} = -p_1\delta_{ij} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial e_{ik}}(\delta_{ij} - 2e_{kj}) \text{ at } p_{ij} \neq 0. \quad (1.3)$$

In these dependencies, p and p_1 are additional hydrostatic pressures. Assuming the medium is isotropic, we take the elastic potential W in the form

$$W = -2\mu J_1 - \mu J_2 + bJ_1^2 + (b - \mu)J_1J_2 - \chi J_1^3 + \dots, \\ J_k = \begin{cases} L_k & \text{at } p_{ij} = 0 \\ I_k & \text{at } p_{ij} \neq 0 \end{cases}, L_1 = d_{kk}, L_2 = d_{ik}d_{ki}, \\ I_1 = e_{kk} - \frac{1}{2}e_{sk}e_{ks}, I_2 = e_{st}e_{ts} - e_{sk}e_{kt}e_{ts} + \frac{1}{4}e_{sk}e_{kt}e_{tm}e_{ms}. \quad (1.4)$$

Here μ, b, χ are the elastic moduli of the medium, and the choice of invariants I_1, I_2 of the deformation tensor in the form (1.4) provides a limiting transition from the second dependence (1.3) to the first when irreversible deformations tend to zero.

We believe that irreversible deformations in the material are accumulated when the stressed state of the loading surface reaches, which, under the conditions of the accepted principle of the Mises maximum, is a plastic potential. As such a surface, we will use the Tresca plasticity condition, generalized to take into account the viscous properties of materials [5], in the form

$$\max|\sigma_i - \sigma_j| = 2k + 2\eta|\varepsilon_k^p|, \tag{1.5}$$

where k is the yield strength, η is the viscosity coefficient, σ_i are the components of the principal stresses, ε_k^p are the components of the principal rates of plastic deformation.

The relationship between the rates of irreversible deformations and stresses is established by the associated law of plastic flow

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^p = \lambda \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma_{ij}}, f(\sigma_{ij}, \varepsilon_{ij}^p) = k, \lambda > 0. \tag{1.6}$$

2. Initial elastic equilibrium

Let an incompressible elastoviscoplastic material, the deformation properties of which are described above, be located between two rigid coaxial cylindrical surfaces: a stationary outer surface, the radius of which is equal to R , and an inner one, with a radius of $r = r_0$, which moves along the z axis. Thus, the solution to this boundary value problem is sought in the cylindrical coordinate system r, θ, z . We will look for it in the class of functions $u = u_z(r, t), V = V_z(r, t), p = p(r, z, t)$. The boundary conditions of the problem are

$$\begin{aligned} u(R, t) &= v(R, t) = 0, \\ v(r_0, t) &= at. \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

We believe that until the moment of time $t_0 = 0$ the material was deformed elastically, and from this moment of time plastic flow begins in the vicinity of the internal (moving) rigid wall. Let us calculate the parameters of this elastic equilibrium state, which is the initial condition for the subsequent process of irreversible deformation. For non-zero components of the deformation tensor in the case under consideration we have

$$d_{rr} = -\frac{1}{2}u'^2, d_{rz} = \frac{1}{2}u', u' = \frac{\partial u}{\partial r}. \tag{2.2}$$

From (1.3), (1.4) and (2.2) for the stress components, accurate to terms of the second order of smallness in the displacement gradient components, we obtain the dependences

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_r &= \sigma_{\theta\theta} = -(p + 2\mu) - \frac{1}{2}(b + \mu)u'^2 = -s, \\ \sigma_m &= -(p + 2\mu) - \frac{1}{2}(b - \mu)u'^2 = -s + \mu u'^2, \\ \sigma_{rz} &= \mu u'.\end{aligned}\quad (2.3)$$

According to equilibrium conditions

$$\sigma_{rz,r} + \sigma_{z,z} + \frac{\sigma_{rz}}{r} = 0, \quad \sigma_{rr} + \sigma_{rz,z} + \frac{\sigma_{rr} - \sigma_{\theta\theta}}{r} = 0. \quad (2.4)$$

s is a function of z only, so $s = az + a_0$. In order for the stresses $\sigma_n, \sigma_{\theta\theta}$ and σ_{zz} to be finite as $z \rightarrow \infty$, it is necessary to set $a = 0$. Then we obtain the solution to the elastic problem in the form

$$\sigma_{rz} = \frac{c}{r}, \quad u = \frac{c}{\mu} \ln \frac{r}{R}, \quad \sigma_{rr} = \sigma_{\theta\theta} = -a_0, \quad \sigma_{zz} = -a_0 + \frac{c^2}{\mu r^2}. \quad (2.5)$$

To find the displacement component, the first boundary condition (2.1) was used. To determine the constant c , we use the plasticity condition (1.5), which in our case takes the form

$$\sigma_{rz}|_{r=r_0} = -k. \quad (2.6)$$

The constant a_0 affects only the distribution of normal stress components. Therefore, it can be considered a given value, both remaining constant during plastic flow and changing with time. The value 0 u , by which it is therefore necessary to shift the inner surface for plastic flow to begin on it, is equal to

$$u_0 = \frac{k}{\mu} r_0 \ln \frac{R}{r_0}. \quad (2.7)$$

The components of reversible deformations according to the found displacement field according to (1.2) are determined by the dependencies

$$e_{rz} = \frac{1}{2} u' = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{k r_0}{\mu r}, \quad e_{rr} = -\frac{3}{2} e_{rz}^2, \quad e_{zz} = \frac{1}{2} e_{rz}^2. \quad (2.8)$$

3. Viscoplastic flow

Let us further assume that, starting from the moment of time $t_0 = 0$, the inner surface moves with speed $v = at, \alpha = \text{const}$. In this case, the developing region of irreversible deformation will be limited by the surfaces $r_0 \leq r \leq r_1(t)$. In the region $\eta_1(t) \leq r \leq R$ the material remains in an elastic state. Let's calculate the parameters of the stress-strain state corresponding to the speed $v^* = at_1 (t \geq t_0)$ at $r = r_0$.

In the region of reversible deformation $r_1 \leq r \leq R$, integrating the equilibrium equation (quasi-static approximation), as before, we find

$$\sigma_{rz} = \frac{c(t_1)}{r}, \quad u = \frac{c(t_1)}{\mu} \ln \frac{r}{R}, \quad v = 0. \quad (3.1)$$

According to the Murnaghan formula (1.3) at $p_{ij} \neq 0$, taking into account the kinematic dependencies (2.8), for the stress components in the plastic flow region we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{rr} = \sigma_{\theta\theta} &= -(p_1 + 2\mu) - 2(b + \mu)e_{rz}^2 = -s_1, \\ \sigma_{zz} &= -(p_1 + 2\mu) - 2(b - \mu)e_{rz}^2 = -s_1 + 4\mu e_{rz}^2, \sigma_{rz} = 2\mu e_{rz}. \end{aligned} \quad (3. 2)$$

On the other hand, integrating the equilibrium equations in the region of plastic flow $r_0 \leq r \leq \eta(t)$, we can obtain

$$s_1 = a_1, \sigma_{rz} = \frac{c_1(t_1)}{r}, e_{rz} = \frac{c_1(t_1)}{2\mu r}. \quad (3. 3)$$

From the conditions of continuity of stress components on the elastoplastic boundary $r = \eta_1(t)$ it follows that $a_1 = a_0, c_1(t_1) = c(t_1)$.

Plastic potential (1.5) in our case will be written in the form

$$f(\sigma_{rz}, \varepsilon_{rz}^p) = \sigma_{rz}^2 - (k - \eta \varepsilon_{rz}^p)^2 = 0. \quad (3. 4)$$

Following the associated law of plastic flow (1.6), from (3.4) we find

$$\sigma_{rz} = -k + \eta \varepsilon_{rz}^p, \lambda = \frac{\varepsilon_{rz}^p}{\eta \varepsilon_{rz}^p - k}. \quad (3. 5)$$

Comparing (3.3) and (3.5) allows us to find the rate of plastic deformation

$$\varepsilon_{rz}^p = \frac{1}{\eta} \left(\frac{c(t_1)}{r} + k \right). \quad (3. 6)$$

Considering that on the elastic-plastic boundary $r = r_1(t), \varepsilon_{rz}^p = 0$, we obtain

$$r_1 = -\frac{c}{k}. \quad (3. 7)$$

Kinematic dependencies

$$\varepsilon_{rz} = \frac{1}{2} v_{z,r} = \varepsilon_{rz}^e + \varepsilon_{rz}^p, d_{rz} = \varepsilon_{rz} + p_{rz}, \quad (3. 8)$$

occurring in the case under consideration, make it possible to find the velocities of points in the region of plastic flow

$$v = \frac{2}{\eta} \left(c \cdot \ln \frac{r}{r_0} + k(r - r_0) \right) + v^*. \quad (3. 9)$$

From the condition of equality of velocities (3.1) and (3.9) on the elastic-plastic boundary $r = r_1$, taking into account (3.7), we obtain an equation for determining the value η_1 corresponding to the value of the velocity $V^* = \alpha t_1$ on the surface $r = r_0$

$$k \left[r_1 \left(\ln \frac{r_1}{r_0} - 1 \right) + r_0 \right] = \frac{\eta \alpha t_1}{2}. \quad (3.10)$$

The displacement in the region of irreversible deformation is found by integration (3.9) up to an arbitrary function $f(r)$

$$u = \frac{2t}{\eta} \left(c \ln \frac{r}{r_0} + k(r - r_0) \right) + v^* t + f(r). \quad (3.11)$$

The function $f(r)$ must be such that the displacements (3.1) and (3.11) and their derivatives u' are continuous at $r = \eta_1$, and also that the displacements (2.7) and (3.11) coincide at $t = t_0 = 0$. Thus, we get

$$f(r) = \frac{c}{\mu} \ln \frac{r}{R}. \quad (3.12)$$

The final solution to the problem of viscoplastic flow is represented by the dependencies:

$$\text{in the elastic region: } \sigma_{rz} = -k \frac{\eta}{r}, \quad u = \frac{k}{\mu} r_1 \ln \frac{R}{r}, \quad v = 0, \quad e_{rz} = -\frac{k}{2\mu} \frac{\eta}{r},$$

$$\text{in the region of viscoplastic flow: } u = \frac{2kt}{\eta} \left(\eta_1 \ln \frac{r_0}{r} + r - r_0 \right) + v^* t + \frac{k}{\mu} \eta_1 \ln \frac{R}{r}, \quad v = \tilde{u}, \quad \varepsilon_{\eta}^p = \frac{k}{\eta} \left(1 - \frac{\eta_1}{r} \right)$$

Reversible deformations, and therefore stresses, in the region of viscoplastic flow are calculated using the same dependencies as in the elastic region. Irreversible deformations according to (1.2) are found in the relations

$$p_{rz} = \frac{kt}{\eta} \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{r} \right), \quad p_{zz} = 2e_{rz} p_{rz}, \quad p_r = 2e_{rz} (e_{rz} + p_{rz}) - \frac{1}{2} u'^2 \quad (3.13)$$

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